

Origin of Right Hand Rule

In classical physics, the right-hand rule is a mnemonic to determine the direction of a vector resulting from a cross product, such as the direction of a magnetic field around a current-carrying wire or the angular momentum of a spinning object. You point your right-hand fingers in the direction of the first vector, curl them toward the second vector, and your thumb points in the direction of the resulting vector. This is expressed mathematically as $\vec{C} = \vec{A} \times \vec{B}$. In QIH, the universe is a lattice of Planck-scale qubits, each represented as a Bloch sphere with a spinning QSV. The direction and rate of change of these QSVs encode velocity, probability, and spacetime curvature. The right-hand rule naturally emerges as a geometric property of how these spinning vectors interact, creating interference patterns that define fundamental forces and the curvature of spacetime.

Visualize a glowing arrow spinning on the surface of the Bloch sphere. This spinning represents the qubit's phase and encodes velocity. When one QSV interacts with another, their combined geometry forms a local "cross product," much like the classical right-hand rule. The cross-product result reflects how probability waves curve around the lattice, creating regions of high or low probability density. For instance, the first vector corresponds to the phase or angular velocity of a QSV on one qubit, the second vector represents the interference pattern with a neighboring QSV, and the resulting vector defines how the probability waves propagate and curve through the lattice, encoding spacetime curvature.

At a larger scale, the holographic screen, such as the event horizon of a black hole, is a high-definition plasma of spinning QSVs. These QSVs act as tiny "blenders," each contributing to the global interference pattern. The right-hand rule helps describe how QSV spin and phase changes create field-like patterns on the holographic screen. The resulting cross-product vectors form the forces and interactions we observe, such as electromagnetic fields or gravitational curvature. The accumulation of these cross-product vectors defines how spacetime bends and how particles move through it.

Imagine a lattice of Bloch spheres, each with a spinning QSV. As one arrow spins, it influences its neighbors, creating a cascade of interference patterns. Point your right-hand fingers in the direction of the first QSV's velocity, curl them toward the phase of the neighboring QSV, and your thumb now points in the direction of the resulting probability density change or curvature. This visualization shows how the geometry of spinning QSVs connects local Planck-scale interactions to global spacetime dynamics.

In QIH, the right-hand rule isn't just a classical mnemonic—it's an emergent property of how quantum information organizes itself in spacetime. The spinning QSVs follow geometric rules that naturally give rise to the cross-product dynamics described by the right-hand rule. This reinterpretation bridges classical physics, quantum mechanics, and holography, offering a unified way to understand how the universe processes information. By connecting this rule to the holographic interference patterns and the motion of probability waves, QIH provides a deeper context for one of physics' most intuitive tools.

In the classical explanation, the right-hand rule is a mnemonic used to determine the direction of a vector resulting from a cross product. For example, in the context of magnetic fields generated by a current-carrying wire, you point your fingers in the direction of the current, curl them toward the direction of the magnetic field, and your thumb points in the direction of the resulting force or angular momentum. This rule describes the spatial relationship between vectors in three-dimensional space and is expressed mathematically as $\vec{C} = \vec{A} \times \vec{B}$, where $\vec{C}$ is the resultant vector of the cross product of vectors $\vec{A}$ and $\vec{B}$.

In Quantum Information Holography (QIH), the right-hand rule emerges as a fundamental property of how spinning Quantum State Vectors (QSVs) on Planck-scale qubits encode information and interact with one another. QIH provides a deeper origin for the right-hand rule by linking it to the interference patterns and phase dynamics of QSVs in the holographic fabric of spacetime.

Imagine spacetime as a lattice of Bloch spheres, each representing a Planck-scale qubit. On each Bloch sphere, a QSV spins and points outward, encoding properties such as velocity, probability, and phase. When two neighboring QSVs interact, the result of their interaction can be described as a cross product. Here's how the classical right-hand rule arises naturally in QIH:

First Vector ($\vec{A}$): This corresponds to the angular velocity or phase of the first QSV on a Bloch sphere. Visualize a glowing arrow spinning on the surface of the sphere. The direction of the arrow represents the velocity or the phase of the QSV.

Second Vector ($\vec{B}$): This is the phase or angular velocity of a neighboring QSV. Its orientation and rate of spin interact with the first QSV, creating a combined effect.

Resulting Vector ($\vec{C}$): The interaction of the two QSVs generates a local "cross-product" vector. According to the right-hand rule, you can point your fingers in the direction of the first QSV ($\vec{A}$), curl them toward the second QSV ($\vec{B}$), and your thumb will point in the direction of the resultant vector ($\vec{C}$).

In QIH, this resultant vector corresponds to the local change in probability density, curvature, or interference patterns in the lattice. The thumb's direction reflects how the interference propagates through the lattice, shaping the fabric of spacetime and encoding fundamental forces such as electromagnetism or gravity.

The classical right-hand rule is thus identical in application, but QIH provides its origin. The geometric alignment and interaction of QSVs on the Planck-scale qubit lattice naturally give rise to the cross-product dynamics described by the rule.